

Construction of Concepts in Geography

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Introduction

Instead of using the traditional goals of teaching behavior or particular skills of instruction, constructivists focus on the theory that emphasizes the careful study of the process by which children create and develop their own knowledge (Strommen & Lincoln, 1998). The classroom is where constructivist theories and practices meet reality. Piaget has shown that there are various stages of cognitive development and that it is constant and ongoing. Social studies teachers using a constructivist approach have a vast array of constructivist strategies that will assist the students with comprehension and study techniques (Robert Jackson, 2006). Using collaborative teaching, peer mentoring, and teacher-guided practice are a few strategies that focus the students on the information to be learned.

The students living on the plains develop their geographical ideas based on the plain lands. They have some peculiar ideas on horizon, distant objects, water bodies water level, changes of states, climatic temperature during their

sensori-motor, pre operation, concrete operation stages in primary and upper primary stages upto class six. They have some general information about the land structure of their state but no in depth understanding about the different places far beyond their places of living. When they learn in bit more detail the geography of the hills and their different characteristics, they incorporate those information with their existing idea of plane land which may be treated as their schema. Thus their individual schema get modified and they interpret the characteristics in terms of their modified schema. They think hill will abide by the different rules of plane land e.g. mountain or higher altitude hills appear to be very near, hills will have water table in it, hill students use cycles, no difficulty of in race along hilly surface. These are the alternative concepts or wrong concepts developed by students and heavily put barrier in the way of developing desirable concepts about the hills [Hawkins, 1978].

The Causes of Development of Misconcepts:
The students of students above class six enjoys formal level of operation. They seek causes or

explanation of different ideas they learn. The geography teacher gives descriptive characteristics of the hills. The physics or physical science teachers present the law of physical phenomena without relating them with the different spheres of life of the students. As a result the students develop wrong speculation about hill, hilly life and environment [Mohapatra,1999]. Guided discussion, demonstration, video show in presence of geography and science teachers might help reconstruction of experience of the students.

Objectives

To design a diagnostic tool for identification of misconceptions related to geographical concepts.

To prepare teaching strategies for remedial teaching in the intervention areas and to see the effect of remedial teaching[

Hypotheses

- Using a constructivist approach school students in grade nine will increase their comprehension in Geography test
- Boys and Girls will differ significantly in construction of experience

Methodology

Sample:

The sample of the present Study comprises students (Boys: 13 & Girls:10) of class IX reading in Schools of Barrackpore of 24 Parganas(N), WB.

Tools:

A passage was prepared comprising the experience of a school girl regarding her tour in the hills and mountains of WB and the

neighbouring states. The girl had some misconceptions about hills and mountains and so she asked for the clarification from her parents who could not satisfy her immediately. Then 10 items were prepared on the basis of observation and the experience of the girl. These items were presented to the students.

The items were SA type each consisting of 2 marks. For objective scoring technique the marks were distributed over different value points. Total time for answering the questions was set as 30 minutes.

Dimensions of the Tool

Visual Angle

Stability

Altitude and temperature

Law of constancy

Principle of habitation

Water table of hills

Characteristics of hilly river

Presation of data:The items were scored and Presented in a frequency distribution table. The mean and SD of the scores were determined.

The misconceptions were identified and the frequency of the misconceptions was tabulated.

Remedial Teaching: A remedial lesson was planned for two periods. Necessary TLM was prepared. Methods of teaching were Group discussion, Teacher pupil interaction, Classroom demonstration.

Retesting:

The test was re-administered and the Mean & SD of the final test were determined. SE_M

was determined to find t value

Results of Analysis was expressed in terms of **t** (Significance of difference)

Table-1

Misconceptions **	(f) in %
Hilly ice naturally formed is not same as ice in market	30
Nearby hilly rivers cause web& tide in small rivers	20
Hilly rivers being very cold unsuitable for swimming	40
For difficulty of boring, tube wells are not sunk in hills	30
No habitation is at the hill top as nothing is available there	35
Excessive blow of air causes coldness at hill	45

** One question was correctly answered by almost all regarding relation between formation of ice and height of the hills. Two questions one on visual angle and another on the stability of the hills could not elicit any clear answer from the students. These three questions were kept out from the remedial teaching but were kept in the post test as usual.

Techniques followed in remedial teaching:

1.Types of ice: First it was admitted that there was a difference of two types of ice as to their sources of availability but

Water in the form of vapour from different water bodies in plain goes to hill top. Again ice

melts and resulting water comes in the the different water bodies of the plain.-comes from the discussion under the guidance of the teacher.

Do you think that that the ice formed at the hill top and ice formed in the factoris differ in composition?

2. Difficulty of swimming in hilly rivers:

Their answer is partly confirmed by saying that coldness may one of the reasons for which it is difficult to swim in hilly rivers but it may not be the total answer.

From the discussion it followed there are:

- i) boulders in the hilly rivers
- ii) thin layer of water
- iii) high speed turbulent motion of water

Have seen all these difficulties in plane rivers?

3. Difficulty of sinking tube wells in the hills:

It is a fact that it is very difficult to bore hills to sink tube wells-this answer is confirmed.

Do you know that petroleum oils are sometimes drawn from the rocky layers by the method of boring? If there is no oil below rock would anybody bore the rock?

Then why is not the tube well sunk below hilly rock to draw drinking water?

Table-2 Mean Score and Standard Deviation and significance of t

Students	N	Before remedial Teaching(X)		After remedial Teaching(Y)		SE _M	t	Sig
		M	SD	M	SD			
Boys	15	6.87	2.15	10.60	2.06	0.76	4.90	S _{.01}
Girls	10	6.70	1.90	12.60	1.56	0.64	9.36	S _{.01}

4. When air blows hill becomes cold. It is not the total answer.

Air blows heavily in Digha but it is not so cold. Then what may be the other reasons for the coldness of hill?

3. Different misconceptions that the students possess regarding geographical characteristics may be significantly eliminated by remedial teaching based on the sharing of experiences and interaction among the students and teachers.

Table-3. Difference of scores in pretest & post test and significance of t

Mean Scores	Boys(B)	Girls(G)	Difference	t	Sig
Pretest(X)	6.87	6.70	0.17	0.20	NS
Post test(Y)	10.60	12.60	2.00	4.25	S _{.01}
Y- X	3.73	5.90	2.17	4.67	S _{.01}

Teacher demonstrated that black bodies become quickly loses heat when shifted from the sources of heat . Hills being mostly black loses heat rapidly at night. So hill becomes colder at night.

There is other reasons also.

Findings : 1. Table 2 indicates that both boys and girls develop in their concepts in Geography after remedial teaching .This confirms hypothesis-1

2. Table 3 indicates initially there is no significance difference between boys and girls in geography concepts. In post test girls significantly sways over boys. Moreover the change in the girls' scores is significantly higher than that of boys' scores. All these considerations prove the veracity of the 2nd hypothesis.

References

- De, K.K. & S. Das (2005) Children's Alternative Concepts About 'Force' and Techniques of Modifying Them. in Vigyan Shikshak (Ed. AK Das) Vol 1/2005, Kolkata A journal of All India Science Teachers' Association (WB).
- Mohapatra, M. (1999): Identification of misconceptions Related to Astronomical Beliefs—Paper presented at International Seminar on researches on School Effectiveness at Primary Stage, July 14-16, 1999, NCERT, New Delhi
- Prabha, S. (1910) Characteristics of Constructivist Classroom in the Context of Science Education. in Journal of Indian Education, May 2010, pp 20-28
- Robert S. Jackson : Using Constructivist Methods to Teach Social Studies to Special Education Students, Masters of Arts in Teaching, 2006 , Wayne State University Detroit, Michigan
- Strommen, Erik F. and Bruce Lincoln (1998). Constructivism, Technology, and the Future of Classroom Learning. International Society for Technology in Education

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